

Supplementary Information - Hierarchical self-assembly of Au-nanoparticles into filaments: evolution and break

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1 Nanoparticles used to assemble nanofilaments

Nanoparticles of different size and geometries (Figure 1) were used to assemble nanofilaments (Figures 2, 3, 4, 5). Most of them are highly symmetrical structures, but others (**b.5**, **b.6** and **b.8**) undergone already structural rearrangement and partial solid-solid transformations such that some peculiarities of their initial form have been lost. Icosahedrons (Ih), Decahedrons (Dh) and Truncated octahedrons (TOh) are the morphologies used. Nanofilaments with no geometrical constraint were assembled employing nanoparticles with same morphology (Figures 2, 3) and mixed morphologies (Figure 4). Nanofilaments in the constrained environment were assembled with mixed morphologies (Figure 5). The case of a single nanoparticle constrained between the electrodes was also investigated (Figure 5).

Figure 1: **Morphologies of the clusters from which our nanofilaments have been constructed, ordered from top left to bottom right with increasing size N .** (a) Icosahedrons, (b) Decahedrons and (c) Truncated Octahedrons. Icosahedrons are noncrystalline structures organized in k shells having a series of magic number $N(k) = \frac{10}{3}k^3 - 5k^2 + \frac{1}{3}k - 1$. They can be thought as polyhedrons with 20 TOh tetrahedra sharing a common vertex, with opposite vertices lying on 5-fold symmetry axis. Decahedrons can be thought as two pentagonal pyramids sharing a common basis, which is composed by (100) facets. They have one single 5-fold symmetry axis which connect two opposite vertices and can be described with a signature of the kind (m, n, p) , where m and n are the sides of (100) facets and p is the depth of the so called Marks reentrance, necessary to make decahedrons stable. Truncated Octahedrons are TOh with a lower surface to volume ratio obtained via cutting the six vertices of an Octahedron. Therefore, they are characterised by a parameter n_l , which is the length of the edges of the original Octahedron, and a parameter n_c , which is the number of cuts applied to the vertices of the original structure. [1].

Figure 2: Nanofilaments with TOh and Ih morphologies. From left to right: 2928-3TOh, 2344-4TOh, 1683-3Ih, 2716-4Ih.

Figure 3: Nanofilaments with Dh and Dh-like morphologies. From left to right: 2149-4Dh-SF, 2661-3Dh-SF, 2733-3Dh-SF.

Figure 4: **Nanofilaments with mixed morphologies.** Top left: 540-Dh-Ih-TOh, 540-Dh-TOh-Ih, 540-TOh-Dh-Ih. Bottom left: 1783-Dh-TOh-Ih, 1783-Dh-Ih-TOh, 1783-TOh-Dh-Ih. Middle right: 2223-Dh-TOh-Ih, 2223-Dh-Ih-TOh, 2223-TOh-Dh-Ih.

Figure 5: **Constrained nanofilaments with mixed morphologies and constrained single-morphology nanoparticles.** Top: 612-Dh-Ih-TOh, 612-Dh-TOh-Ih, 612-TOh-Dh-Ih. Bottom: 147-Ih, 201-TOh, 192-Dh.

2 Coalescence of large nanofilaments (> 2000 atoms)

Large free nanofilaments tend to coalesce into ellipsoids, passing through drastic structural changes. Inter-clusters grain boundaries are quickly eliminated in some cases, depending on geometry and size. Single and multi-fold twinning are frequently detected, whilst a tendency in reordering towards a crystalline state is generally observed and quantified through an increase in the 421 CNA signature. Free nanofilaments 2716-4Ih, 2149-4Dh-SF, 2928-3FCC and the mixed structures composed by 2223 atoms were examined. A general trend of Ih-assembled nanofilaments to transform into Dh and/or FCC is found [2], whilst TOh nanofilaments at this size and temperature are confirmed to be the more stable [3], despite the fact that rearrangement towards a more favourable energy state can still be observed. The evolution of free nanofilaments stability with time is reported in Figure 6. Statistics have been collected over both different geometries and initial atomic velocities on a time-scale of 50 ns. Different simulations showed similar results. It can be seen that the excess energy is strongly affected by the size and geometry taken in consideration. TOh nanofilaments are very reluctant to undergo phase transitions, especially when having a size of 2928 atoms. However, 2344-4TOh shows a steady decrease in its Δ , meaning that structural transformations are occurring at a slow pace. Icosahedral nanofilaments appear to be very fast-changing. In fact, phase transitions develop within a nanosecond for both 2716-4Ih and 1683-3Ih, with the latter reaching a lower energy due to the smaller size and less grain boundaries to overcome when trying to reorder. The decahedral nanofilament 2149-4Dh-SF appear to have a faster phase transitions rate than 2716-4Ih within the first nanosecond, but we observe that is not always the case, as between 2.5 and 4 ns the two systems have equal energy. From that moment onwards, decahedra keep transforming with two further transitions whilst icosahedra only undergo another one. It is peculiar that they both drastically change around 7 ns. The mixed structures reach essentially the same excess energy of 3.475 ± 0.025 eV, although they slightly differ in pace and it can be said that 2223-FCC-Ih-FCC achieves the lowest energy, highlighting the efficiency of icosahedra to merge with both Dh and FCC. Indeed, 2223-FCC-Dh-Ih takes longer to reach its final energy, undergoing two net phase transitions at approximately 5 and 16 ns, without considering the first one occurring at the very beginning. It is assumed that the slower pace of 2223-FCC-Dh-Ih is motivated by the fact that decahedral five-fold symmetries do not favour merging with TOh and Ih at the same time.

2.1 Union of 5-fold symmetry axis in 2716-4Ih

Figure 7 shows the transition from an Ih-nanofilament to a Dh-like structure on a time-scale of 8 ns. It can be noticed that 421, 422 and 555 CNA signatures change symmetrically throughout the process. Precisely, the 422 signature decrease corresponds to the breaking of grain boundaries whilst 555 decrease represents the disappearance of local five-fold symmetries. The prominent development of 421 means an increase in the crystallinity of the system. Indeed, the non-zero value of 422 and 555 suggests that the newly formed crystals are misoriented, so that grain boundaries, precisely five-fold twinning planes, persist. Figure 8 illustrates the nanofilament spatial extension. It can be seen that the centre of mass and gyration, which is the average distance traveled by the centre of mass, is minimized and it takes the form of an ellipsoid. Moreover, the radius of gyration indicates that the

Figure 6: **Stability of nanofilaments:** evolution of excess energy with time. Top: same morphology nanofilaments. Bottom: mixed nanofilaments.

conformation of the system tends to reach spherical symmetry, confirming the achievement of an elliptical shape. The deformation along the cartesian axis shows a clear tendency of the x, y and z lengths to reach a unique value, with the z-axis remaining elongated, with a length of approximately 4 nm.

Figure 7: **2716-4Ih bulk CNA evolution.** Twin boundaries are marked by red lines whilst FCC order by green. Grey atoms are not recognised. (A) Sintering of small icosahedrons in the middle (800 ps). (B) The newly formed structure in the middle shares one five-fold symmetry axis with the cluster at the bottom and it is trying to reach the one at the top (800ps-2.5ns). (C) The bulk is almost fully connected in a 421 fashion but there are still grain boundaries. (D) Dh-like structure characterised by a five-fold twinning which is maintained throughout the whole process (100 ns).

2.2 Multi-fold twinings in 2149-Dh-SF

The assembled decahedral-like nanofilament adopted different crystal structures separated by multi-fold twin boundaries. Whilst the formation of twinings in the icosahedral nanofilament was fast and there was a clear preference towards five-fold symmetry, the decahedral nanofilament appears to do so with a slower pace without a specific preference for twinings, as reported in Figures 9, 10 and 11.

Moreover, we have seen that it also arranges itself into an ellipsoid. However, the fact that the radius of gyration steadily keeps decreasing suggest that the various grain boundaries could break on a longer time-scale, allowing the crystal planes to join together.

Figure 8: **Deformation parameters.** Top left: centre of mass gyration. Top right: Deformation along Cartesian axis. Bottom left: radius of gyration. Bottom right: Dh-like structure resultant of Au2716-4Ih after 100 ns simulation of canonical ensemble.

Figure 9: **2149-4Dh-SF CNA evolution.** Twin boundaries are marked by red lines whilst fcc is marked by green. Grey atoms are not recognised. (A) Increase of both 421 and 422 at the very beginning of the simulation (3.45 ns). (B) Further increase in crystallinity and breaking of grain boundaries, but no precise symmetries identified. (C) Formation of a five-fold twinning in the cluster at the bottom. (D) Formation of multi-fold twinings with four or more intergrown fcc stacking.

Figure 10: **Deformation parameters.** Top left: deformation along cartesian axis. Top right: resultant of 2149-4Dh-SF with a five-fold twinning highlighted. Bottom: radius of gyration.

Figure 11: **Perspective views of 2149-4Dh-SF resultant.** (A) Two two-fold boundary separated by a stacking fault. (B) A hint of a two-fold boundary. (C) fcc stacking resulting from the quasi-crystalline structure placed in the middle of the former nanofilament. (D) A two-fold twinning very close to be a three-fold.

3 Nanofilament deformation parameters of short nanofilaments

Figure 12: Gyration and deformation parameters.

Radius of gyration and x, y, z deformation parameters of in vacuum NPs with no geometrical constraint show a sphericisation process. The final NPs have a radius of gyration ~ 2.5 nm after 100 ns.

4 Layer by layer analysis

4.1 Individual nanoparticles

Figures 13, 14 and 15 illustrate the pair distance distribution functions and layer by layer analyses of 201-FCC, 192-Dh and 147-Ih respectively. The positions of the PDFs peaks show a good agreement with bulk gold at 300K and 1 atm, as the first peak is at 2.88 Å, and the second at 4.07 Å, reflecting nearest neighbours distances and lattice constant of a gold crystal structure. However, the fact that the third peak, which corresponds to local deviations from the stacking sequence, is higher and wider than the others suggest that the structures have several stacking faults and holes. Indeed, this can be noticed by inspecting the configuration of each layer. Precisely, viewing the xy-plane from the bottom we noticed that the first layer of both FCC and Ih has a stacking fault after the second and third atomic row respectively, while Dh accomplished a good ABA (HCP) rearrangement mimicking the (111) surface. Second layers are smaller in size, a hole is observed in the second row of the Ih and a stacking fault is detected after the third row in the FCC, while Dh showed a good rearrangement again. It is in the third layer that Dh starts showing some imperfections, with visible dislocations in the third and fourth rows. Many other defects can be detected inspecting the following layers of all the structures. Generally, it can be said that both CCP and HCP piling are observed. Precisely, a clear ABC sequence is observed in the electrode, layer one and two by viewing the Dh (Figure 14) along the z-axis. The same pattern is detected viewing the Ih (Figure 15) from the top. On the other hand, viewing the Ih from the bottom up, as well as the whole piling sequence of the FCC (Figure 13), reveal an ABA stacking. It is clear that such patterns are not perfect and the presence of a huge number of defects must be highlighted, yet some interesting tendencies have been seen. For instance, the tendency of the Ih structure to form two twins pyramidal structures could be useful in explaining the mechanism behind the breaking of of FCC-Dh-Ih. The coordination number per layer and the atom count per layer are indeed lower for the Ih case (Figure 18).

Figure 13: **PDF and layer by layer analysis of 201-FCC.** Top: pair distance distribution function. Bottom left: view of the whole nanostructure with reduced atomic radius along the z-axis. Bottom right: view of each layer across the xy-plane.

Figure 14: **PDF and layer by layer analysis of 192-Dh.** Top: pair distance distribution function. Bottom left: view of the whole nanostructure with reduced atomic radius along the z-axis. Bottom right: view of each layer across the xy-plane.

Figure 15: **PDF and layer by layer analysis of 147-Ih.** Top: pair distance distribution function. Bottom left: view of the whole nanostructure with reduced atomic radius along the z-axis. Bottom right: view of each layer across the xy-plane.

Figure 16: **Constrained FCC between (111) planes.** Stratification of TOh_{201} between (111) planes occurs with a coordination number per layer 11 $> \text{CNL} \geq 12$.

Figure 17: **Constrained Dh between (111) planes.** Stratification of Dh_{192} between (111) planes occurs with a coordination number per layer 11 $> \text{CNL} \geq 12$.

Figure 18: **Constrained Ih between (111) planes.** Stratification of Ih_{147} between (111) planes occurs with a coordination number per layer $10 > CNL \geq 11$. Atom count decreases in the middle of the NF, approaching ~ 12 atoms (close to break).

Figure 19: **Layer by layer analysis of Dh-Ih-FCC.** Left: view of the whole nanostructure with reduced atomic radius along the z-axis. Right: view of each layer across the xy-plane.

Figure 20: **Layer by layer analysis of Dh-FCC-Ih.** Left: view of the whole nanostructure with reduced atomic radius along the z-axis. Right: view of each layer across the xy-plane.

Figure 21: **Layer by layer analysis of FCC-Dh-Ih.** Left: view of the whole nanostructure with reduced atomic radius along the z-axis. Right: view of each layer across the xy-plane.

References

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